

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL CONSTANTS AND BIOLOGICAL DATA OF MANNICH BASES OF 2-ALKYL/ARYL-3-BENZIMIDAZOLYLQUINAZOLIN-4(3H)-ONES (IV) AND THEIR ANTHELMINTIC ACTIVITY

Sl. No.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	X	m.p. °C	Mol. formula	% Inhibition	
							<i>H. nana</i>	<i>N. brasiliensis</i>
1*	C ₆ H ₅	I	- piperidine	C ₆ H ₄	172-75	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ N ₆ OI	99	37
2.	C ₆ H ₅	I	- morpholine	C ₆ H ₄	168-70	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ N ₆ O ₂ I	—	—
3.	C ₆ H ₅	I	- N-CH ₃ - piperidine	C ₆ H ₄	249-50	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ N ₆ OI	—	—
4.	C ₆ H ₅	I	- 4-CH ₃ - piperidine	C ₆ H ₄	220-24	C ₂₄ H ₂₈ N ₆ OI	—	—
5*	C ₆ H ₅	Br	- piperidine	C ₆ H ₄	223-25	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ N ₆ OBr	50	36
6*	C ₆ H ₅	Br	- morpholine	C ₆ H ₄	197-200	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ N ₆ OBr	Inactive	Inactive
7.	C ₆ H ₅	Br	- N-CH ₃ - piperidine	C ₆ H ₄	249-51	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ N ₆ OBr	—	—
8.	C ₆ H ₅	Br	- 4-CH ₃ - piperidine	C ₆ H ₄	220	C ₂₄ H ₂₈ N ₆ OBr	—	—
9.	C ₆ H ₅	H	- piperidine	C ₆ H ₄	185	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ N ₆ O	—	—
10*	C ₆ H ₅	H	- morpholine	C ₆ H ₄	189-90	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ N ₆ O ₂	71	39
11*	C ₆ H ₅	H	- pyrrolidine	C ₆ H ₄	179-80	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ N ₅ O	57	Inactive
12.	C ₆ H ₅	H	- 4-CH ₃ - piperidine	CH ₂ -C ₆ H ₅	110	C ₂₄ H ₂₈ N ₆ O	—	—
13.	C ₆ H ₅	H	- piperidine	-CH-COOH CH ₂ -C ₆ H ₅	215-17	C ₂₅ H ₃₀ N ₆ O	—	—
14.	<i>o</i> -Nitro-phenoxy	H	- piperidine	-CH-COOH C ₆ H ₄	140-42	C ₂₆ H ₃₀ N ₆ O ₂	50	Inactive
15.	<i>o</i> -Nitro-phenoxy	H	- morpholine	C ₆ H ₄	195-97	C ₂₅ H ₃₀ N ₆ O ₂	—	—
16*	-CH ₃	H	- morpholine	C ₆ H ₄	215-17	C ₂₇ H ₃₀ N ₆ O ₂	64	—
17*	-OH ₂	H	- piperidine	C ₆ H ₄	268	C ₂₆ H ₃₀ N ₆ O	50	43
18.	-CH ₃	H	- N(OH ₂) ₂	C ₆ H ₄	255-56	C ₂₆ H ₃₂ N ₆ O	43	35

Infrared data : Disappearance of a peak between 1850-1587 cm⁻¹ for C=O group indicates the formation of benzimidazole ring and utilization of acid carboxylic group.

Analytical data : C, H and N were found within the range of experimental error.

* Screened for anthelmintic activity.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank the Head, Department of Chemistry, Lucknow University for facilities, Dr. J. C. Katiyar, Department of Parasitology, C. D. R. I., Lucknow for biological screening of the compounds and I. C. M. R., Delhi for the award of a Junior Research Fellowship to one of them (B. K.).

References

1. E. C. TAYLOR and J. BARTULIN, *U. S. Patent*, 3,476, 756; *Chem. Abs.*, 1970, 72, 43718u.
2. R. J. ALAIMO and C. J. HATTON, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1972, 15, 108.
3. A. MACKIE and A. L. MISRA, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 3919, 4430.
4. R. R. BELL, T. J. GALVIN and R. D. TURK, *Amer. J. Vet. Res.*, 1962, 23, 185.
5. E. R. AMES, J. M. CHENEY and R. RUBIN, *Amer. J. Vet. Res.*, 1965, 26, 668.
6. M. M. ENDICOTT, B. W. ALDEN and M. L. SHERRILL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 1303.
7. A. S. WHEELER and W. M. OATES, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 32, 770.
8. C. J. KLEMMME and J. H. HUNTER, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1940, 5, 227.
9. V. H. WALLINGFORD, H. G. DECKER and M. KRUTY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 4365.
10. S. S. TIWARI and V. K. PANDY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, 51, 440.

11. M. T. BOGERT and H. A. SEIL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, 29, 517.
12. S. S. PARMAR and R. C. ARORA, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1967, 10, 1182.
13. D. W. HEIN, R. J. ALHEIM and J. J. LEAVITT, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 79, 427.
14. H. J. HORN, *Biometrics*, 1956, 12, 311.
15. J. S. STEWARD, *Parasitology*, 1955, 45, 255.
16. J. H. WHITLOCK, *J. Parasitology*, 1943, 29, 42.

Thin Layer Chromatographic Analysis and Characterisation of Some Substituted Maleianilic Acids

NEPAL SINGH*, POONAM AGRAWAL, VINITA GUPTA and

B. R. SARAN**

Department of Chemistry, Hindu College, Moradabad

Manuscript received 28 January 1982, revised 22 April 1983, accepted 3 August 1983

SUBBA Rao¹ characterized some aromatic primary amines as a derivative of corresponding phthalianilic acid. In the present study twelve maleianilic acids were prepared and characterized by melting

* Author for correspondence; 42, Malviya Nagar, Moradabad-244 001.

** Department of Chemistry, K. G. K. College, Moradabad.

TABLE 1—NITROGEN ANALYSIS AND CHARACTERISTIC IR ABSORPTION BANDS OF MALEIANILIC ACID DERIVATIVES

Sl. No.	Amine condensed with maleic anhydride	Maleianilic acids obtained	N% Found (Calcd.)	Characteristic ir amide bands (cm ⁻¹)		
				I	II	III
1.	<i>o</i> -Amino phenol	2'-Hydroxy ₂ maleianilic acid	6.72 (6.78)	1653	1563	1282
2.	<i>m</i> -Amino phenol	3'-Hydroxy maleianilic acid	6.80 (6.74)	1653	1563	1299
3.	<i>p</i> -Amino phenol	4'-Hydroxy maleianilic acid	6.70 (6.76)	1620	1550	1288
4.	<i>o</i> -Toludine	2'-Methyl maleianilic acid	6.72 (6.82)	1655	1553	1290
5.	<i>m</i> -Toludine	3'-Methyl maleianilic acid	6.82 (6.82)	1647	1563	1316
6.	<i>p</i> -Toludine	4'-Methyl maleianilic acid	6.75 (6.82)	1653	1563	1307
7.	<i>o</i> -Nitro aniline	2'-Nitro maleianilic acid	11.62 (11.86)	1625	1520	1282
8.	<i>m</i> -Nitro aniline	3'-Nitro ₂ maleianilic acid	11.90 (11.86)	1625	1520	1282
9.	<i>p</i> -Nitro aniline	4'-Nitro maleianilic acid	11.37 (11.86)	1630	1520	1299
10.	<i>o</i> -Chloro aniline	3'-Chloro maleianilic acid	5.85 (6.20)	1653	1563	1290
11.	<i>m</i> -Chloro aniline	3'-Chloro maleianilic acid	6.30 (6.20)	1653	1563	1290
12.	<i>o</i> -Sulphanilic acid	4'-Sulpho maleianilic acid	5.01 (5.16)	1620	1520	1292

TABLE 2—SPOT COLOUR AND R_f VALUES OF SUBSTITUTED MALEIANILIC ACIDS IN DIFFERENT SOLVENTS

Sl. No.	Maleianilic acid	Spot colour	Solvent					
			Ethyl acetate	Methyl acetate	Acetone	Dioxane	Dioxane + Benzene (3 : 1 v/v)	Methyl cyanide + Ethyl acetate (1 : 2 v/v)
1.	2'-Hydroxy maleianilic acid	Redish yellow	0.38	0.92	0.63	0.84	0.48	0.88
2.	3'-Hydroxy maleianilic acid	Yellow	0.40	0.90	0.76	0.16	—	0.47
3.	4'-Hydroxy maleianilic acid	Green	0.13	0.23	0.84	0.52	0.52	0.68
4.	2'-Methyl maleianilic acid	Light yellow	—	0.90	0.96	0.62	0.71	0.86
5.	3'-Methyl maleianilic acid	White	0.21	0.94	0.93	0.89	0.54	0.52
6.	4'-Methyl maleianilic acid	Yellow	—	0.91	—	0.80	—	0.68
7.	2'-Nitro maleianilic acid	Yellow	0.95	0.98	0.92	0.86	0.90	0.94
8.	3'-Nitro maleianilic acid	Light yellow	—	0.60	—	0.52	0.42	0.42
9.	4'-Nitro maleianilic acid	Light brown	0.33	0.80	0.71	0.74	0.76	0.71
10.	2'-Chloro maleianilic acid	Yellow	0.85	0.76	0.55	—	—	0.80
11.	3'-Chloro maleianilic acid	Dirty white	0.32	—	0.19	—	—	0.43
12.	4'-Sulpho maleianilic acid	Dirty white	0.75	—	0.76	—	0.70	—
	Time (min) required for 10 cm development		10.20	8.10	8.10	34.45	85.30	20.25

point, elemental analysis and ir spectra. The maleianilic acids were detected and separated by using 0.25 mm layer silica gel (G) on a glass plate. The hydroxy, methyl, nitro and chloro substituted isomers of maleianilic acids can be resolved very successfully in methyl cyanide-ethyl acetate (1 : 2 v/v) and dioxane-benzene (3 : 1 v/v) mixtures.

Experimental

Equimolar solutions of the primary amines and maleic anhydride after refluxing in benzene were mixed and shaken well and left aside at room temperature. The products were filtered, washed

repeatedly with benzene and dried. Purification was made by bicarbonate method¹. The condensation of maleic anhydride and aromatic amines takes place as follows :

Thin layer chromatography : Silica gel (G) (E. Merck) was used for preparing 0.25 mm layer. The plates (15 × 10 cm) were dried at 100°. Alcoholic solutions of the maleianilic acids were spotted on the dry plates and the plates developed upto 10 cm in a

saturated chamber with suitable solvent at room temperature ($27 \pm 1^\circ$). The spots of coloured maleianilic acids were clearly visible. The colourless spots were identified in iodine vapours. The R_f values of the compounds in different solvents are recorded in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

A critical study of the R_f values reported in Table 2 shows that the substituted maleianilic acids can be successfully resolved in dioxane, ethyl acetate and ethyl acetate-methyl cyanide (2:1 v/v), dioxane-benzene (3:1 v/v) mixtures. It is also observed that *o*-nitro derivatives have higher R_f values than the *m*-nitro derivatives in the above solvents. The *m*-methyl derivatives have higher values in methyl cyanide and dioxane. Methyl cyanide-ethyl acetate mixture (1:2 v/v) resolved all the substituted isomers.

It has also been observed that the *ortho* derivatives have higher R_f values in dioxane-benzene (3:1 v/v) mixture and dioxane, whereas the *meta* derivatives have lowest R_f values (except methyl derivatives in dioxane) in these solvents. The colour of the spots in different solvents appears to be the same. Maximum trailing of the spots were observed in acetone.

IR studies :

Amides usually show three bands with strong absorptions near 1640 (amide I), 1550 (amide II)^{4,5} and 1305-1200 cm^{-1} (amide III)^{4,5}. In the present maleianilic acids, the respective amide ir absorption bands were observed at 1653-1625, 1553-1520 and 1307-1282 cm^{-1} . The ir absorptions of three amide bands in *ortho* and *meta*-nitro substituted maleianilic acids (1625, 1520 and 1282 cm^{-1} , respectively) have lowest value whereas *para* methyl substituted derivatives (1653, 1563, 1307 cm^{-1}) have highest value among the prepared acids. The *meta* substituted hydroxy and chloro maleianilic acids have higher ir frequencies for amide I and II bands (1653, 1563 cm^{-1} and 1653, 1563 cm^{-1}), respectively.

References

1. N. V. SUBBA RAO and C. V. RATNAM, *J. Sci. Indus. Res.*, 1962, **21B**, 45.
2. L. J. BRILLAMY, *The Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules*, John Wiley and Son, N. Y., 2nd Edn., 1966, p. 209.
3. T. RICHARD, "The Chemistry of Penicillin", Princeton University Press, 1949, p. 390.
4. G. SVEHLA (Ed.), "Comprehensive Analytical Chemistry", Elsevier, New York, 1976, p. 293.
5. E. DAVIES and I. JONES, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1955, **51**, 761.